

275 kW/m² CD = 0.001 mm t = 900 s

350 kW/m² CD = 0.001 mm t = 120 s

275 kW/m² CD = 1.3 mm t = 900 s

350 kW/m² CD = 1.3 mm t = 120 s

275 kW/m² CD = 2.0 mm t = 900 s

350 kW/m² CD = 2.0 mm t = 120 s

